

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-182-IA-2% 40 0.5 rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	66	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400 40 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 182
Injection Volume:	5.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/13/2022 6:35:01 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 11:36:03 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	12.382	873181	4.10	56105
2	12.978	866229	4.07	55099
3	13.539	9922905	46.59	587282
4	14.539	9635253	45.24	544592

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-183-IA-2% 40 05 rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	4	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400 40 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 2 183
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/4/2023 15:45:52 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 11:33:26 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	12.371	162355	1.67	8687
2	13.006	13079	0.13	737
3	13.689	90	0.00	31
4	14.442	9550040	98.20	471401